

SYNTHESIS OF CARBON NANOTUBES AND ITS APPLICATIONS IN FLEXIBLE FIELD EMISSION DEVICE AND COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Synthesis of Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) was performed through the cold-walled and the hot-walled chemical vapor deposition (CVD) processes. CNTs in the forms of fluff and cable were produced in hot-walled horizontal and vertical tube furnaces, respectively; on the other hand, patterned CNTs were synthesized in the cold-walled CVD chamber. Depending on the designed form of CNTs, different processing routes and catalyst systems need to be used. On the application of patterned CNT array in the flexible field emission device, the transferred technique was used and a low turn-on voltage of 1.13 V/ μm with the enhanced factor of 6,222 was achieved. On the application of fluff CNTs in the field of nanocomposites, hybrid nanocomposites containing CNTs and short carbon fibers were fabricated, and comparisons of mechanical properties among composites reinforced with short carbon fibers, CNTs, and hybrid reinforcements were made. Microstructures of the as-synthesized CNTs were examined by the Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM), and fracture morphologies of the nanocomposites were examined by the Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM).

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, chemical vapor deposition (CVD), field emission, nanocomposites

INTRODUCTION

Since the discovery of carbon nanotube in 1991, numerous of studies were reported on the syntheses, characterizations, and applications of the carbon nanotubes (CNTs)[1-5]. The proposed methods for the synthesis of CNTs include arc discharge, laser ablation, and chemical vapor deposition (CVD)[6-8], and the thermal chemical vapor deposition method is the most promising method for mass production. Depending on the application of CNTs, researchers adopted different CVD processes for synthesizing CNTs; for example, plasma-enhanced CVD was frequently adopted for synthesizing vertical aligned CNTs on substrate for field emission application, whereas thermal CVD was used for mass production.

In the thermal CVD process, the most frequently adopted route is conducting mixture of precursors of hydrocarbon, catalyst, and promoter to the high temperature chamber, which was so-called the floating catalyst method. The mechanism for the floating catalyst method includes decomposition of catalyst precursor and formation of metal catalyst clusters. At the same time, promoter precursor decomposes and adsorbs onto the surface of the catalyst cluster, the local temperature at the promoter-absorbed area on cluster surface is reduced, which is benefit for CNT growth. The decomposed carbon species absorbed on the cluster surface are dissolved into the cluster and segregated when saturated, which forms CNTs. Depending on the size of the local melting area, single- and multi-walled CNTs can be synthesized. The mechanism for CNTs growing from substrate is similar to the foregoing description, except that the catalysts in the form of thin films are pre-placed onto the substrate before CNT growth.

In general, the processing of the traditional short fiber reinforced polymeric composites, such as extrusion, injection molding, etc. can be used for fabricating CNTs reinforcing nanocomposites. Although extremely high mechanical properties were demonstrated in the tensile test of a single CNT, the increase in strength of the CNTs reinforced composites is limited, as compared with the fiber reinforced composites. It is due to low weight percentage of CNTs that can be introduced into the matrix and poor CNT/matrix interfacial strength.

Field emission device is regarded as one of the most feasible applications of CNTs in commercialized products in the near future. Actually, a small size display using CNT emission light as the back light was demonstrated. One of the advantages using CNTs as the electron emitters is a high aspect ratio of CNT, and electrons can be emitted at relatively low voltage due to enhancement of electric field around the CNT tip. The demonstration of electron emission from the CNT emitter embedded in plastic substrate may open a new era for flexible light source.

In this work, CNTs and CNT array were synthesized using both the hot-walled and the cold-walled CVD processes. Nanocomposites reinforced with fluffy(network) CNTs and pulverized CNTs were fabricated and their mechanical properties were compared. Furthermore, mechanical properties of the hybrid nanocomposites reinforced with short carbon fibers and CNTs were also investigated. The transfer process of CNTs from a silicon substrate to a polycarbonate substrate is introduced and the field emission property of the flexible device with low turn-on voltage is demonstrated.

EXPERIMENTS

Hot-wall CVD for CNTs

Fluffy and cable single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) were synthesized through the floating catalyst method in a horizontal and a vertical, respectively, mullite tube furnace below 1200 °C. In this work, xylene, thiophene, ferrocene, and hydrogen were adopted as precursors of carbon source, promoter, catalyst, and carrier gas, respectively. The details can be found in our previous published article[9]. The multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) can also be obtained by using proper processing parameters. In general, the processing window for SWCNTs is narrower than that of the MWCNTs.

Cold-wall CVD for CNTs

An ultra high vacuum CVD chamber was designed for the growth of vertical aligned CNTs (VA-CNT) array. Various catalyst systems were adopted and were sputtered onto the substrate pre-patterned by the photolithographic method. For the field emission device, VA-CNT was grown on a SiO₂/Si substrate using patterned catalyst (Co/Ti) as the catalyst. The mixture of 10% H₂/Ar (30 sccm) gases was introduced into the reactor at the pressure of 10 Torr. Once the temperature of 550⁰C was reached, the C₂H₂ gas, acted as carbon precursor, was channeled into the reactor at a flow rate of 60 sccm to grow CNTs. The details of the experimental design can be found in reference [10]. The height of CNT array can be controlled by adjusting synthesis temperature and period.

Fabrication of Nanocomposites

Fabrications of nanocomposites using fluffy MWCNTs, pulverized MWCNTs, and fluffy SWCNTs obtained from the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method, were performed. The thermosetting phenolic resin, PF-650, was used as the matrix. Different weight percentages, 0.5~ 4.0 wt%, of MWCNTs were added to PF-650 phenolic resin and mixed by magnetic stirrer. The details of preparation of CNTs/phenolic nanocomposites can be found in reference [11]. Mechanical properties of the CNTs/phenolic nanocomposites, the short carbon fibers (CFs)/phenolic composites, and the MWCNTs/CFs/phenolic hybrid nanocomposites were tested and the results were compared. For fabricating nanocomposites containing CFs, a proper amount of carbon fibers was cut to a length of 1 mm and mixed with the phenolic resin to fabricate the CFs/phenolic composites and MWCNTs/CFs/phenolic nanocomposites.

Fabrication of flexible field emission device

The SiO₂/Si substrate, with the as-synthesized VA-CNTs on it, was placed on a hot plate with temperature maintained at 170⁰C, and a piece of polycarbonate (PC, T_g=150⁰C, T_m=267⁰C, 500 μm thickness) sheet with proper size was placed on the SiO₂/Si substrate. By applying a proper force, VA-CNTs were penetrated into the semi-melted polycarbonate at 170⁰C. Then the PC substrate was separated from SiO₂/Si substrate. The transferred process can be carried out easily and shortly, it takes less than 30 min to finish the VA-CNT growth and CNT transfer.

Field emission tests

The field emission property measurement was carried out using Keithley 237 under a pressure lower than 10⁻⁵ torr. During the measurement, a distance of 300 μm between anode and cathode was kept.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The appearances of the as-synthesized MWCNTs, SWCNTs, and VA-CNTs are shown in Fig. 1. The insets show the Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) images of the CNTs. The MWCNTs, with diameters in the range of 40~60 nm, are twist each other. In

order to compare the influence of CNT continuity on the mechanical properties, the MWCNTs were then pulverized until the length of 2~10 μm was reached. On the other hand, the SWCNTs, with the diameters in the range of 0.8~1.5 nm and in the form of bundle which are entangled to form fluffy structure, was used as the reinforcements.

The tensile strength of the nanocomposites, reinforced with fluffy (network) MWCNTs, pulverized MWCNTs, fluffy SWCNTs, and pulverized MWCNTs mixed with carbon fibers, and the composites reinforced with short carbon fibers are shown in Fig.2. It is obvious that the tensile strength of the nanocomposites was enhanced even very small amount of CNTs were introduced. On the other hand, the tensile strengths of most of the nanocomposites reach a plateau if the CNT amount over 1.5 wt% were introduced.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 1 Appearances of CNTs and the TEM images (a)fluffy MWCNTs, (b)fluffy SWCNTs, (c)VA-CNTs

Although the tensile strength of the network MWCNTs/phenolic nanocomposites increases with the increasing of MWCNT up to 4.0 wt%, the increasing rate becomes slow for the nanocomposites reinforced with MWCNTs at the amount over 2.0 wt%. The tensile strength of the network MWCNTs/phenolic nanocomposites reaches 87.4 MPa when 4.0 wt% network MWCNTs was added. The tensile strengths of the network MWCNTs/phenolic nanocomposites are higher than those of the pulverized MWCNTs/Phenolic nanocomposites in all the cases studied in this study. The pulverized MWCNTs/Phenolic nanocomposites have higher tensile strengths than those of the carbon fiber/phenolic composites except at 0.5 wt% specimens. The hybrid/phenolic nanocomposites showed the lowest tensile strength. It implies that the rule of mixtures can not be used in the analysis of tensile strength of the hybrid nanocomposites.

Figure 2 Tensile strength of the nanocomposites reinforced with fluffy MWCNTs, pulverized MWCNTs, fluffy SWCNTs, pulverized MWCNTs + carbon short fibers and the composites reinforced with short carbon fibers [11-13]

The comparison of Young's modulus was made and the magnitude with the order of network MWCNTs/phenolic > pulverized MWCNTs/phenolic > hybrid/phenolic > carbon fiber/phenolic at a specific CNT weight percent was detected, as shown in Fig. 3. The Young's modulus increase with the increasing of reinforcements is obvious; however, the nanocomposites reinforced with SWCNTs behave very differently. It is due to difficult to achieve uniform dispersion of the SWCNTs in phenolic matrix.

Field emission properties of the as-synthesized VA-CNTs were tested. Fig. 4 shows the Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM) image of the VA-CNTs after transfer to PC substrate. The VA-CNT pattern can be well maintained after transfer. The inset on the lower-left corner of Fig. 4 shows the photo image of the flexible CNTs-based field emission device with the size of 1.0 cm² and the photographs of fluorescent light image pictured from the front of the plate cathode. The light intensity increased with applied voltage. Very low turn-on voltage of 1.13 V/μm with the enhanced factor of 6,222 was achieved for the transferred CNT-based flexible field emission device.

Figure 3 Young's modulus of the nanocomposites reinforced with fluffy MWCNTs, pulverized MWCNTs, fluffy SWCNTs, pulverized MWCNTs + carbon short fibers and the composites reinforced with short carbon fibers [11-13]

Figure 4 Field emission properties of the VA-CNT array on flexible substrate.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the fluffy and cable SWCNTs were synthesized in a hot-walled tube furnace through the CVD process and VA-CNTs was produced in a cold-walled CVD process. The tensile strength and the Young's moduli of the nanocomposites reinforced with different reinforcements were tested, and the results showed that the mechanical properties increased with CNT contents even very small amount of CNTs were introduced. Hybrid nanocomposites reinforced with SWCNTs and short carbon fibers showed the lowest tensile strength. VA-CNTs transferred from Si substrate to flexible PC substrate was perform and the emission current increases with the applied voltage is also observed.

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